

Typed BNF: Backend-independent Semantic Actions

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Abstract

Semantic actions (SAs) enable type-safe construction of Abstract Syntax Trees (ASTs), but the existing ones break the portability of grammars. A grammar that uses SAs is accepted by one backend and cannot be reused in another one, where a backend refers to a parser generator under a specific programming language.

This paper proposes Typed BNF, a BNF variant that includes SAs. Constructs such as SAs, terminals and non-terminals are type-checked by our dedicated type system, which is proved to be sound with respect to the natural semantics of parsing. Guided by the type information, a grammar of Typed BNF is transpiled into grammars accepted by different parser generators, where the included SAs are transpiled into the corresponding programming languages. Typed BNF brings portability while retaining SAs and producing ASTs. Its success of supporting various parser generators under multiple architectures (currently, ANTLR4, Lark, and OCaml Menhir) suggests the effectiveness of our proposal. Comparisons against directly using the backends are given, showing the portability, type safety and capability of producing ASTs using Typed BNF.

1 Introduction

A parser generator accepts a context-free grammar typically written in Backus-naur form (**BNF**) and generates a parser. Such generated parser usually runs in the target language (backend language). As can be seen from Fig. 1.1, the generated parser accepts the source language (frontend language) described by the grammar and produces concrete syntax trees (**CSTs**, or **parse trees**¹).

Figure 1.1: Example: frontend language, BNF, parser and CST

¹ASTs are distinguished from CSTs in this paper. “Abstract syntax trees, or simply syntax trees, differ from parse trees because superficial distinctions of form, unimportant for translation, do not appear in syntax trees”[1].

Figure 1.2: Semantic actions

Despite the proliferation of parser generators, it is preferable to generate parsers with the following three properties: portability, AST output, and type safety. Portability is important when an existing parser is needed in a different programming environment, where a portable parser helps avoid reimplementing. AST output means that the parser can output Abstract Syntax Trees (**ASTs**¹), where ASTs are preferred rather than CSTs in many uses of parsers such as compilers and program processing [13]. Type safety helps statically detect errors, especially for those that occur in constructing ASTs.

In terms of the above three properties, we argue that the existing systems can achieve part of them, but not all. This fact is detailed below.

A common existing approach is to create a parser that outputs CSTs. Such a parser can be generated from grammars that are portable in the existing systems, and the required ASTs are gained by writing a CST-to-AST converter in the backend language. This approach seemingly achieves portability and AST output. However, portability is not fully achieved since the part of AST construction is not portable and has to be implemented per backend. Worse, type safety is missing, since in current implementations of portable parsers, CSTs are restricted to be a universally typed tree in ANTLR4² [9] and others [3] [7], which raises a type safety issue considerably close to that of functional un|parsing [2].

Another common approach is to use semantic actions (SAs). An SA is a piece of code assigned per production rule to custom the parsing results (i.e., semantic values [12]). In Fig. 1.2, `func($1, $2)` is an SA. SAs can create ASTs, and can be statically checked if the backend language is statically typed. However, SAs force the mixture of code and grammar (Fig. 1.2), where the code is written in a specific backend language. An existing implementation of SAs achieves AST output and type safety, but breaks the portability.

There can be other approaches, but as long as we know, none of the existing systems satisfy all the requirements of portability, type safety and AST output.

With the above motivation, we propose Typed BNF, a variant of BNF that allows the mixture of SAs and grammars. Grammars are transpiled to be acceptable to one of many parser generators, and SAs are transpiled into the backend language to achieve portability. Instead of using an existing programming language to write SAs, we design a minimal programming language named *Simpler* to ease transpilation. This is because correctly transpiling a production-ready programming language is unrealistic, and it is rare to write complex programs in SAs.

The crucial point of Typed BNF and *Simpler* is that we assign types to their language constructs such as terminals, nonterminals, and SAs. As can be seen from Fig. 1.2, the output AST is created using the user function `func`, plus `$1` and `$2` which are respectively the semantic values of `a` and `b`. Hence, the types of `$1`, `$2` and `func` are related. Such static type information contributes to the subsequent type checking/type inference, and helps the transpiler appropriately choose how to encode values and types into the backend language. To assign types for Typed BNF, a modified Damas-Hindley-Milner (HM [4]) type system is introduced.

A positive result has been shown when applying our proposal in practice. Without modifying the core part of the reference implementation of Typed BNF, we have supported transpilation targeting four backends under three parser generator architectures: ANTLR4

²ANTLR4 generates different classes for different nonterminals, and the sub-trees are stored in a homogeneous list: <https://www.antlr.org/api/Java/org/antlr/v4/runtime/tree/ParseTree.html>

<pre>File "lua.mly", line 251, characters 44-46: Error: This expression has type B but an expression was expected of type A</pre>	<pre>File "lua.tbnf", line 251, column 44-46: at rule 'prefixexp': prefixexp : prefixexp "." NAME args { CallMethod(\$1, \$4, \$3) } in 'CallMethod(\$1, \$4, \$3)' '\$4' expected type A, but has B</pre>
---	---

Figure 1.3: Error messages: Menhir versus Typed BNF

<pre>binop → "-" { isBinOp(\$1) } ... unaryexp → "-" expr { isUnaryOp(\$1) } ...</pre>	<pre>function f(a, b, ...) 1 - -g(a, b, c()) end</pre>
---	--

Figure 1.4: Context-aware syntax highlighting "(" and "-" via Typed BNF

[9], Menhir [12] and Python Lark [7]. Currently, these architectures in total support more than four programming languages, and the supported list is growing.

A direct implication of using Typed BNF is that we guarantee the type safety of AST construction while keeping the grammar and SAs portable to other backends, i.e., “one grammar, type-checked parsers producing desired ASTs everywhere.”

Despite the existence of other approaches, Typed BNF is advantageous due to the following reasons:

- Typed BNF brings type safety, portability and AST output at the same time. Besides, we proved that if a grammar is type-checked by our type system, parsing using the grammar always produces data of the expected type.
- Typed BNF understands types, which allows automatic type inference. Unlike SAs in ANTLR4 [9] or YACC [6], type annotations are usually not mandatory. This considerably eases the use of semantic actions.
- Typed BNF allows the generated parsers to output ASTs across backends. This is particularly important to scenarios where a user requires parsers but also wants to avoid concrete syntax and focus on the abstract syntax.
- Typed BNF performs static type checking before code generation, and reports compile-time errors with precise positions and extra information such as rule names (Fig. 1.3). Pre-generation type checking is usually not available in the existing systems, which makes Typed BNF appealing even when portability is not needed.
- Typed BNF statically checks the grammar and AST construction, even if the backend language is dynamic.

In addition, a few unexpected but impressive uses of Typed BNF have been observed. Such uses reduce the required workload by a large margin in practice. An instance is syntax highlighting, which usually requires a significant amount of works to get correct, and things get worse when considering context-aware syntax highlighting. Fig. 1.4 shows how Typed BNF is used to highlight "(" , ")" , and "-" in different syntactic structures, where in this paper the symbol \rightarrow is used to be distinguished from the metasymbol $::=$. We have implemented a cross-editor syntax highlighter³ for the Lua language⁴, which demonstrates how effortless Typed BNF could be in such tasks. More details are provided in Section 5.2.

³A cross-editor syntax highlighter for Lua, via Typed BNF: <https://github.com/thautwarm/cross-editor-syntax-highlighter>

⁴Lua 5.3 Reference Manual: <https://www.lua.org/manual/5.3/manual.html>

In summary, we make the following contributions:

1. We propose Typed BNF, with which we successfully achieve all of type safety, portability and AST output.
2. We formalise a type system for Typed BNF and the language Simpler, raise type safety issues of a grammar (Def. 3), and prove that a grammar checked by our type system is type safe, i.e., a successful parsing always produces Simpler expressions that have expected types.
3. With Typed BNF, we make it possible for users to be unaware of the concrete parser generator implementation and distribute parsers to different environments. Users then have no need to consider which parser generator to use at first, but choose a backend after finishing the parser tasks.
4. We give a reference implementation, with which we have successfully supported backends such as ANTLR4+C#, Lark+Python, Menhir+OCaml, and ANTLR4+TypeScript, allowing users to switch parsers between such four programming languages.
5. As a bonus, we find scenarios such as creating cross-editor syntax highlighters, where Typed BNF reduces the amount of works by a large margin (Section 5).

In Section 2, we give an overview of Typed BNF to build intuition for readers. Section 3 presents (1) the syntactic definitions of the core language, (2) definitions about semantics of parsing, (3) a type system of Typed BNF and (4) the proof of type safety of grammar. In Section 4, a few common issues in cross-backend transpilation are addressed, answering why the type system is designed as in Section 3. Section 5 compares parsing using Typed BNF versus directly using the backends, showing additional merits of using Typed BNF. Section 6 compares our works with related research. Section 7 gives conclusion and future works of this research.

2 Overview

Typed BNF is a derivative of Backus-naur form. Each grammar has 3 parts:

1. **Definitions and external declarations.** This part defines data types and their constructors, and declares external types and variables.
2. **Parsing rule definitions.** This part includes definitions for nonterminals.
3. **Lexical rule definitions.** This part uses a regular-expression language to define non-literal terminals. These lexical rules are transpiled into valid input accepted by the backend lexer generator.

We firstly introduce a minimal example, i.e., a Typed BNF implementation of lambda calculus, to help build intuition. Formal definitions of Typed BNF’s language constructs will be given in Section 3.

2.1 Definitions and external declarations of datatypes and values

Typed BNF allows defining and declaring datatypes and values in the grammar to simplify AST construction.

We can define constructors for the types defined in the grammar. For instance, a parser for untyped lambda calculus produces a value of `Expr` type (Fig. 2.1). As can be seen, three constructors are defined in a form similar to Haskell GADTs:

$$C : (\tau_1, \dots, \tau_n) \rightarrow \tau_0$$

where C is a constructor here.

```

type Expr
case EApp : (Expr, Expr) -> Expr
case EVar : string -> Expr
case ELam : (string, Expr) -> Expr

```

Figure 2.1: Expr datatype and constructors

```

extern type Expr
extern var EApp : (Expr, Expr) -> Expr
extern var EVar : string -> Expr
extern var ELam : (string, Expr) -> Expr

```

Figure 2.2: External Expr type and constructors

These facilities further enhance portability by reusing AST construction across backends and clarifying the specification of output ASTs, allowing users to focus on the abstract syntax and strip away the concrete syntax. This is considerably important in scenarios for language processing such as analyzing, simulating, measuring and synthesizing programs [13]. For instance, the metaprogramming tool OCaml PPX [8] accepts OCaml ASTs as input and outputs the transformed ASTs. In such cases, even if the concrete syntax slightly changed from version to version, users can skip them and focus on ASTs.

However, there are also inevitable circumstances that a user needs to define ASTs outside the grammar. This is achievable by Typed BNF's external definitions. For instance, the grammar given in Fig. 2.2 is very similar to that from Fig. 2.1. The difference is that the types and values marked "**extern**" in the latter grammar should be provided externally.

Another use of external declarations is to access utility values (including functions) in a backend-independent approach. For instance, string-to-integer conversion is common in SAs, but different programming languages have different ways to access this operation. Such gap is filled by Typed BNF's external declarations (e.g., `parseInt` in Fig. 2.3).

2.2 Parsing rule definitions

A nonterminal in Typed BNF is defined using a parsing rule definition.

Fig. 2.4 shows a part of the grammar for untyped lambda calculus, where `name` is a nonterminal and `NAME` is a terminal. A nonterminal definition takes one or more productions; a production is a sequence of terminals and nonterminals, and is followed by an SA that is an expression written in Simplr.

A terminal such as `NAME` always has a semantic value typed `token`. Incidentally, `token` is necessarily a built-in type constant, as it is required in theoretical parts (Section 3.1).

`$1, $2, ..., $n` that occur in SAs are used to access semantic values of production elements. For instance, `$1` in the definition of `name` stands for the semantic value of `NAME`.

2.3 Lexical rule definitions

Lexical rules are not part of Typed BNF, but we present them to help build intuition.

In practice, we want to support literal terminals (e.g., a terminal written as `'fun'`) and generate a pair of parser and lexer from a single grammar. Supporting literal terminals requires the compiler to automatically extract the corresponding lexical rules from the pars-

```

extern var lexeme      : token -> string
extern var parseInt   : string -> int

```

Figure 2.3: External utility values

```

name → NAME           { lexeme($1) }
atom → name           { EVar($1) }
      | "(" expr ")"   { $2 }
expr → "λ" name "." expr { ELam($2, $4) }
      | expr atom      { EApp($1, $2) }
      | atom           { $1 }

```

Figure 2.4: Example of productions in Typed BNF

```

ignore SPACE
SPACE = ' ' | '\t' | '\r' | '\n'
START = 'a' .. 'z' | 'A' .. 'Z' | '_'
FOLLOW = START | '0' .. '9'
NAME = START FOLLOW*

```

Figure 2.5: Lexical rules for untyped lambda calculus

ing rules. Besides, generating a correct, efficient lexer requires knowing all lexical rules in advance. We take the easy approach: users write lexical rules in the grammar. Such rules are translated into the backends, in order to leverage the backend-specific lexer generator.

As for the lambda calculus grammar, the lexical rules for non-literal terminals are given in Fig. 2.5, while the lexical rules for literal terminals are automatically extracted from parsing rules.

Names of lexical rules such as `NAME` and `START` in Fig. 2.5 represent terminals, only if they are referenced in any production. For more details, readers are referred to the manual⁵ of Typed BNF.

3 Type System

In this section, we firstly introduce a core language of Typed BNF. Then, we introduce a type system for such core language, and prove that such type system enjoys a certain soundness property.

The key idea of our type system comes from studying the demands of transpiling Typed BNF (Section 3.3): rejecting polymorphically typed parsing results.

3.1 Core language, and types

We firstly introduce the symbols used in Fig. 3.1.

C denotes a predefined value from Σ (Section 3.4), i.e., a constant, external variable or a constructor that may appear in the language `Simpler`; w denotes a token expression that may appear in the language `Simpler`; η denotes a nonterminal in the context-free grammar; t denotes a terminal in the context-free grammar; v denotes a variable in the language `Simpler`; i, n, k denotes integers that may appear in the language `Simpler`, or the suffixes of terms in this paper.

The core language of Typed BNF is given in Fig. 3.2, where the symbol e denotes a `Simpler` expression whose definition is given in Fig. 3.3.

As can be seen from Fig. 3.2, each production has the form $\eta \rightarrow a_1 \cdots a_n \{e\}$, where a_i is a terminal or nonterminal, and e is an expression in the language `Simpler`. This expression retrieves the results from the production elements a_1, \cdots, a_n , and creates an AST as the result of parsing using η . The accurate definition of parsing using a terminal/nonterminal is given in Section 3.2. Besides, we have $n \geq 1$, as we intentionally avoid ϵ production rules.

⁵Typed BNF Documentations: <https://github.com/thautwarm/Typed-BNF/blob/main/documentations.md>

C	predefined values	w	tokens
η	nonterminals	t	terminals
v	variables	i, n, k	integers

Figure 3.1: Basic symbol definitions

a	$::= t$	(terminals)
	η	(nonterminals)
p	$::= \eta : a_1 \cdots a_n \{e\} \quad (n \geq 1)$	(productions)
G	$::= p_1 \cdots p_n$	(grammars)

Figure 3.2: Typed BNF core

In Fig. 3.3 we define expressions of the language `Simpler`. (e_1, \dots, e_n) is a tuple of n elements; $e_f(e_1, \dots, e_n)$ is the application of function e_f on e_1, \dots, e_n ; $\$i$ retrieves the semantic value of the i -th production element in the production in its left side; let $v = e_1$ in e_2 binds e_1 to a variable v in expression e_2 ; fun $(v_1, \dots, v_n) \Rightarrow e$ is a function that takes n arguments v_1, \dots, v_n and returns e .

Types of Typed BNF are defined in Fig. 3.4 where T is a type constant such as integers; $(\tau_1 \cdots \tau_n) \Rightarrow \tau_r$ is the type for n -ary functions; F^i is a type constructor that takes exactly i type parameters and comes from Σ (Section 3.4); $\langle \alpha_1 \cdots \alpha_n \rangle \tau$ is a polymorphic type (polytype) similar to the universal type $\forall \alpha_1 \cdots \alpha_n. \tau$ in ML or Haskell except that the parameters α_i of the former are ordered.

e	$::= v$	(variables)		
	w	(tokens)	τ	$::= T$ (type constants)
	C	(predefined values)		α (type variable)
	(e_1, \dots, e_n)	(tuples)		$\tau_1 * \cdots * \tau_n$ (product types)
	$e_f(e_1, \dots, e_n)$	(applications)		$F^n \langle \tau_1 \cdots \tau_n \rangle$ (generic types)
	$\$i$	(i -th components)		$(\tau_1 \cdots \tau_n) \Rightarrow \tau_r$ (function types)
	let $v = e_1$ in e_2	(let-bindings)	σ	$::= \tau$ (monotypes)
	fun $(v_1, \dots, v_n) \Rightarrow e$	(functions)		$\langle \alpha_1 \cdots \alpha_n \rangle \tau$ (polytypes)

Figure 3.3: `Simpler` expressions

Figure 3.4: Types

3.2 Semantics of parsing

This subsection defines the semantics of parsing.

Let us first assume that there is an injective mapping L that maps a terminal to a token. The intuition behind L is that we have a lexer that converts an input string to a sequence of tokens, and, for each terminal t , there exists a unique token w matched by t , namely, $L(t) = w$. Note that a token is also an expression in `Simpler`.

We now define a 4-ary relation $\bar{w} \xrightarrow[a]{G} e$, where $\bar{w} = w_1 w_2 \cdots w_n$.

To understand this, we have to notice that the grammar symbol a is also a parsing rule. Then, we can read $\bar{w} \xrightarrow[a]{G} e$ as “ a parses \bar{w} under the grammar G and produces e ”, where e is

a semantic value of a .

Definition 1. Given a grammar G , a non-empty sequence of tokens $\bar{w} = w_1w_2\cdots w_n$, a G -grammar symbol a and a Simpler expression e , we inductively define $\bar{w} \xrightarrow[a]{G} e$ as follows:

- If a is a terminal t of G and $L(t) = w$, then $w \xrightarrow[a]{G} w$ holds.
- If a is a nonterminal η of G , $\bar{w}_1\cdots\bar{w}_k$ is a partition of \bar{w} , $\bar{w}_i \xrightarrow[a_i]{G} e_i$ for each $i \in \{1, \dots, k\}$, and there exists a production $p=(\eta \rightarrow a_1\cdots a_k \{e_0\}) \in G$, then $\bar{w} \xrightarrow[a]{G} e$ holds where

$$e = \text{let } v_1 = e_1 \text{ in } \cdots \text{let } v_k = e_k \text{ in } \{\$i \mapsto v_i\}e_0$$

and $\{\cdot \mapsto \cdot\}$ is a substitution⁶.

If $\bar{w} \xrightarrow[a]{G} e$ holds, we say a parses \bar{w} and produces e under G . Note that \bar{w} is restricted to be non-empty, as we exclude an ϵ -production rule in G . Thanks to this restriction, the above parsing 'process' is well defined.

3.3 Design issue of the type system

Our goal is to design a suitable type system for our Typed BNF, and prove that, if a grammar G type-checks, any successful parsing using G would result in a well-typed expression in our language, and is then converted to a well-typed expression in the backend language.

This goal is not trivial as one may expect at the first sight: Suppose we design a naive type system without any restrictions, given G , a , and \bar{w} , the relation $\bar{w} \xrightarrow[a]{G} e$ holds for various e s of radically different types; it can be a polymorphic type, and as its instances, the type of some e and that of another e' can be incompatible. This is undesirable, because we need to map a type in Typed BNF into the one in backend systems (explained in Sec. 4.1) that usually do not allow polymorphically typed parsing results. Then, allowing polymorphic types for the parsing results would result in compile errors in the backend.

This dangerous fact suggests a minimum requirement for the type system: for a given a , there must exist a type τ such that, for all \bar{w} and e , if $\bar{w} \xrightarrow[a]{G} e$ holds, then e has the type τ .

A trivial solution is to design a poor type system for Typed BNF. For instance, we assume that there was only one type in our system (e.g., the universal type Object) so that the minimum requirement can be automatically satisfied. However, such a solution is impractical. As we map types in Typed BNF into those in the backend, the generated AST should have only one (monomorphic) type. In such cases, it is tough for the backend language to manipulate the parsing results, making our Typed BNF useless. Hence, our goal is to find a trade-off that keeps the rich structure of a type system, and at the same time, rejects grammars not satisfying the minimum requirement.

Based on this observation, we introduce a subsystem of the Hindley Milner (HM) type system, which is widely used in the ML language family, and its subsystem is advantageous due to the following considerations:

1. Good trade-off: The HM type system is a simple but expressive type system, and is particularly easy to translate into a backend language. Such property promises Typed BNF a good trade-off of expressiveness, simplicity and backend compatibility.

⁶We use $\{x \mapsto t\}$ to denote substitutions to avoid possible confusion between $[t/x]$ used by Haskell Curry and $[x/t]$ used by Alfred Tarski.

2. Type soundness: By making sure any type assignment in our type system is valid in the ordinary HM type system, type soundness is automatically derived, which tells that certain bad behaviors of programs never happen in our system.

Let us state the desirable property for the type system, which is introduced in the next subsection. Here we assume that Λ is a type system that assigns types to closed expressions e in Typed BNF.

Definition 2. (Typing)

Given a grammar G and a type system Λ that assigns types to expressions (denoted by $\Lambda e : \tau$), a grammar symbol a has the type τ under G and Λ iff $\forall \bar{w} \forall e (\bar{w} \xrightarrow[a]{G} e \Rightarrow \Lambda e : \tau)$.

We write $a :_{\Lambda}^G \tau$ if a has the type τ under G and Λ .

Definition 3. (Type safety of grammar)

A grammar symbol s is type-safe under G and Λ iff there exists a type τ such that $a :_{\Lambda}^G \tau$.

A grammar G is type-safe under a type system Λ iff, any grammar symbol in G is type sound under G and Λ .

As discussed above, our goal is to design a subsystem of HM, subject to grammar typeability.

$\boxed{\Omega \vdash_a a : \tau}$	$\Omega \vdash_a t : \text{token} \quad (\eta \mapsto \tau) \Omega \vdash_a \eta : \tau$
$\boxed{\tau \sqsubseteq \sigma}$	$\frac{\tau' = \{\alpha_i \mapsto \tau_i\} \tau}{\tau' \sqsubseteq \langle \alpha_1 \cdots \alpha_n \rangle \tau} \text{(SPEC-INST)}$ where $\{\alpha_i \mapsto \tau_i\} \tau$ denotes replacing a_i with τ_i in τ
$\boxed{\Gamma \vdash_e e : \tau}$	$\Gamma \vdash_e w : \text{token} \quad (v \mapsto \tau) \Gamma \vdash_e v : \tau \quad \frac{\Sigma(C) = \sigma \quad \tau \sqsubseteq \sigma}{\Gamma \vdash_e C : \tau} \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash_e e_i : \tau_i}{\Gamma \vdash_e (e_1, \dots, e_n) : \tau_1 * \dots * \tau_n}$
	$\frac{\Gamma \vdash_e e_f : (\tau_1 \cdots \tau_n) \Rightarrow \tau_r \quad \Gamma \vdash_e e_i : \tau_i \text{ (for } i = 1, \dots, n\text{)}}{\Gamma \vdash_e e_f(e_1, \dots, e_n) : \tau_r}$
	$\frac{\Gamma \vdash_e e_1 : \tau_1 \quad (v \mapsto \tau_1) \Gamma \vdash_e e_2 : \tau_2}{\Gamma \vdash_e \text{let } v = e_1 \text{ in } e_2 : \tau_2} \text{(LET)} \quad \frac{(v_1 \mapsto \tau_1) \cdots (v_n \mapsto \tau_n) \Gamma \vdash_e e : \tau_r}{\Gamma \vdash_e \text{fun } (v_1 \cdots v_n) \Rightarrow e : (\tau_1 \cdots \tau_n) \Rightarrow \tau_r}$
$\boxed{\Omega \vdash_p p \text{ is-valid}}$	$\frac{\Omega \vdash_a \eta : \tau \quad \Omega \vdash_a a_i : \tau_i \quad v_1, \dots, v_n \text{ are fresh} \quad e' = \{\$i \mapsto v_i\} e \quad (v_1 \mapsto \tau_1) \cdots (v_n \mapsto \tau_n) \vdash_e e' : \tau}{\Omega \vdash_p \eta \rightarrow a_1 \cdots a_n \{e\} \text{ is-valid}} \text{(PROD-VALID)}$
$\boxed{\Omega \vdash_G G \text{ is-valid}}$	$\frac{\forall p \in G \quad \Omega \vdash_p p \text{ is-valid}}{\Omega \vdash_G G \text{ is-valid}} \text{(G-VALID)}$

Figure 3.5: Typing rules

3.4 Typing Rules

We give a type system for our language as a set of typing rules.

We have the judgement $\Omega \vdash_p p$ is-valid to examine if a production rule p is valid under a type assignment Ω for all nonterminals where

$$\Omega = (\eta_1 \mapsto \tau_1) \cdots (\eta_n \mapsto \tau_n)$$

Two typing rules for Typed BNF are referenced by \vdash_p . The first of which, $\Omega \vdash_a a : \tau$, judges if a grammar symbol a has the monotype τ under Ω . The second of which, $\Gamma \vdash_e e : \tau$, judges if a Simpler expression e has the monotype under the typing context for variables Γ where

$$\Gamma = (v_1 \mapsto \tau_1) \cdots (v_n \mapsto \tau_n)$$

Besides, we have an implicit global environment Σ holding the information, with which we know types of constants. We use notation to query such information from Σ as follows:

- $\Sigma(C) = \sigma$ iff the predefined value C has the polytype σ . A predefined value can be a constant, a constructor or an external variable.

The complete typing rules are given in Fig. 3.5. The judgement $\Omega \vdash_G G$ is-valid examines if the whole grammar G is valid under the type assignment Ω . The unique typing rule for this judgement (the rule at the bottom) states that it holds if and only if all productions rules in G are valid. As can be seen, most typing rules are nearly identical to those in the HM type system, but differ in the rules **SPEC-INST** and **LET**, where we rule out automatic generalization and unordered type parameters in polytypes. The reason for such a design is given in Sec. 4.2.

We say that G type-checks iff $\Omega \vdash_G G$ is-valid is derivable for some Ω .

To relate the type system in this subsection with the parametric type system Λ in the previous subsection, we define a type system Λ^s for closed expressions as follows:

Definition 4. $\Lambda^s e : \tau \iff \emptyset \vdash_e e : \tau$

3.5 Type soundness and its proof

We are ready to state the main theorem for our type system.

Theorem 1. If a grammar G type-checks in the above type system, then G is type sound under Λ^s .

Proof. Suppose $\Omega \vdash_G G$ is-valid is derivable for some G and Ω . For any grammar symbol a , $\Omega \vdash_a a : \tau$ holds for some τ , therefore, the next lemma (Lemma 1.1) is a sufficient condition for the theorem to hold. \square

Lemma 1.1. Given G and Ω such that $\Omega \vdash_G G$ is-valid, then we have that for any symbol a and type τ ,

$$\Omega \vdash_a a : \tau \implies \forall \bar{w} \forall e (\bar{w} \xrightarrow[a]{G} e \implies \Lambda^s e : \tau)$$

The proof is omitted.

4 Backend Translation

Translating Typed BNF into a backend is simple: a backend provider accepts the typed AST of a grammar and generates input (code and grammar) accepted by the new backend.

The following subsections address a few common issues that happen during backend translation, part of which also gives the reason why we design our system as it currently is.

4.1 Data encoding

The Simpler programming language (Fig. 3.3) provides many convenient programming features to write SAs, many of which might not be directly supported in the backend. This issue forces us to consider how to encode them into the backend, and our principle is to prioritize the interoperability between the backend language and Simpler.

Such principle can be explained by how Typed BNF supports sum types. Sum types [11] can simplify the routines of creating ASTs. However, transpiling sum types is difficult, and needs different solutions from language to language. For instance, we have to consider how to translate Simpler data structure into the backend programming language. Consider a programming language from the C language family. Such a language usually has classes and interfaces. In this case, a sum type is translated into an interface, while constructors are translated into classes that implement the interface. Even if a sum type has other encodings that may produce a performance gain (e.g., a pair of "tag" and unknown data), we still prefer the interface-class encoding, because other encodings are far from the idiomatic abstractions in a C-like programming language and unfriendly to interoperability.

4.2 Parametric polymorphisms

Parametric polymorphisms (also known as generics or templates) are widely supported in different programming languages. For interoperability concerns, we prefer to make translated types look similar to the original types in the language Simpler, and intend to make such type translation a one-to-one correspondence.

However, there are two main issues against our target:

- In most programming languages, local functions cannot be polymorphic. Such fact prevents us from supporting let-polymorphisms (**LET** in Fig. 3.5) and forces us to adopt a modified **LET** rule.
- In most programming languages, type parameters of polymorphic types are ordered, while they are unordered in the HM type system. This forces us to adopt a modified type specialization rule (**SPEC-INST** in Fig. 3.5).

4.3 Interoperation mechanism

For parser generators that support SAs, the way of accessing external code varies. To address the discrepancies, a user needs to declare external symbols (for both types and values) in Typed BNF, and implementations should be given somewhere in the backend.

Providing such implementations have to be backend-specific. For instance, in C#, parsers are usually generated as a partial class, and thus external symbols can be implemented by extending the same-name partial classes; while in OCaml, the external symbols can be encapsulated into a specific module type, and the generated parser becomes a module functor that accepts such a specific module.

The principle here is, providing implementations should never modify an existing grammar. For instance, we should allow users to customize how to map an identifier of Simpler into the backend language, as the ordinary one might be invalid or undesired. Consider declaring an external function. It can take the name "data" which could be a keyword in a backend language. Another case is when we want to link an external symbol to an existing symbol in the backend language (e.g., people might link "json" to "Object" for JavaScript). A Typed BNF is never aware of the existence of a specific backend.

4.4 Success of the proof of concept

In this subsection, we have discussed the issues happened in backend translation.

Figure 4.1: Interoperations in different backends: OCaml and C#

As can be seen, each of the above three case studies requires us to solve one or more issues; nevertheless, we have successfully addressed the three cases. We have gradually implemented backends such as Menhir+OCaml, ANTLR4+C#, Lark+Python. The newest backend, ANTLR4+TypeScript is made easy, by slightly modifying the code for ANTLR4+C#. Implementing a new backend with such minor efforts suggests the effectiveness of our approach.

5 Results

5.1 Comparisons against backends

We have achieved portability while keeping type safety and AST output. A range of backends have been implemented, including ANTLR4, Lark, and Menhir. The currently covered programming languages are C#, Python, OCaml and TypeScript.

Furthermore, we have conducted a series of experiments using Typed BNF. For each full-featured backends (ANTLR4+C#, Lark+Python and Menhir+OCaml), for each grammar (JSON and Lua), parser implementations are created using Typed BNF (norm group) versus manually using the corresponding backend (control group). Such parsers use SAs to create the same ASTs in a type-safe way. The total code size (including grammars) for a group is used as the criteria.

We have also made experiments for cross-editor syntax highlighting. In such cases, we compare the size against the corresponding editor’s standard method for syntax highlighting. These experiments use two editor systems: Visual Studio Code and Spyder IDE. The corresponding standard methods of syntax highlighting are tmLanguage and Pygments, respectively.

The results are given in Table 1. We explain the meaning of each column:

1. The first column means the tested grammar. We experiment on JSON and Lua, and parse those languages from real-world codebases.
2. The second column means the backend we compare against. The programming language used by the backend is omitted in the table. With ANTLR4 we use C#, with Lark we use Python, and with Menhir we use OCaml. Specifically, “(VSCoDe SH)ANTLR4” means that the ANTLR4+TypeScript backend is used for VSCode syntax highlighting; “(Pygments SH)Lark” means that the Lark+Python backend is used for Pygments

Grammar	Backend	Size(norm group)	Size(control group)	Ratio of workload saved
JSON	ANTLR4	882C/36L+(628C/24L)	2651C/87L	43.04%
JSON	Lark	882C/36L+(220C/13L)	547C/32L	-101.5%
JSON	Menhir	882C/36L+(622C/24L)	934C/53L	-61.03%
Lua	ANTLR4	5904C/209L+(1083/65L)	17441C/493L	59.94%
Lua	Lark	5904C/209L+(277C/13L)	8750C/378L	29.36%
Lua	Menhir	5904C/209L+(637C/31L)	5544C/377L	-17.98%
Lua	(VScode SH)ANTLR4	932C/35L+(2255C/103L)	12075C/785L	73.61%
Lua	(Pygments SH)Lark	932C/35L+(1624C/62L)	3030C/115L	15.64%

Table 1: Experiment results (SH = syntax highlighting)

syntax Highlighting.

3. The third column indicates the code size of the norm group’s implementation. For instance, "882C/36L+(628C/34L)" means 882 characters/36 lines in Typed BNF, and 628 characters/34 lines in the backend programming language, i.e., in total “1510C/70L”. Although character count is a more accurate criteria, we include line count here to give intuitive sense of the workload. Generated code is ignored.
4. The fourth column indicates the code size of the same implementation made by control group. Generated code is ignored.
5. The fifth column gives percentages computed against

$$1 - \frac{\text{character count(norm group)}}{\text{character count(control group)}}$$

showing the percentage of saved workload when using Typed BNF. Larger is better, and a negative percentage means directly using the backend requires less workload than using Typed BNF.

As can be seen in row 1-3, row 4-6 and row 7-8 of the table, Typed BNF targeting different backends can share the same grammar. This shows our success in portability. Besides, the code size of using Typed BNF, is always larger than that of using Menhir. This is because the language used in Typed BNF, Simpler, is strictly a weaker subset of OCaml. Moreover, Typed BNF needs extra declarations for several basic operations (e.g., `parseInt`) for being backend-independent, while in OCaml we directly access these operations.

However, we have observed that as the grammar gets larger, the ratio of workload saved by Typed BNF significantly increases. For the simplest grammar, i.e., JSON, Lark outperforms Typed BNF by a large margin, but for the Lua grammar, the code of using Typed BNF becomes much more concise than that of using Lark. To explain this, we assess that as the grammar gets larger, the conciseness of Typed BNF is approaching Menhir, because we have borrowed many concrete syntaxes from Menhir. Also, the basic operations needed to be externally declared do not increase when the grammar gets larger.

For syntax highlighting (Table 1, row 7-8), we modify the existing Lua grammar by removing code for AST construction and inserting code for syntax highlighting. Hence, we only count additional changes to the existing grammar, i.e., “932C/35L” in the table.

In addition, Typed BNF does not cause performance gain or loss under a proper implementation of external values and types. Thanks to the interoperability-friendly data encoding (Section 4.1), Typed BNF can generate nearly identical code to that of directly using the backends.

<code>Catch1.</code>	<code>Catch ::= "catch" "(" TypeSpec Ident ")" Body;</code>
<code>Catch2.</code>	<code>Catch ::= "catch" "(" TypeSpec ")" Body;</code>

Figure 6.1: BNFC: a piece of Java grammar

5.2 Syntax highlighting

Incidentally, a new syntax highlighting approach³, as a by-product of our research, shows the merit of our system in practice.

Syntax highlighters created using our system is beneficial due to the following properties:

1. Cross-editor. Due to Typed BNF’s backend-independent nature, syntax highlighters can be generated for different editor systems.
2. Correct. Syntax highlighters by our system are grammar-based. A grammar precisely describes the syntax, which allows the derived syntax highlighter to access correct text segments in the correct syntactic structures. However, syntax highlighters that use other methods, such as `tmLanguage`, usually require the developers to re-design automata which occasionally breaks in corner cases.
3. Efficient. Although automata specialized to syntax highlighting can be more efficient, syntax highlighting does not hit the peak performance of a parser generator. For instance, our TypeScript-ANTLR4 backend can highlight 50,000 lines of Lua code per second, which is sufficient for rendering the texts that appear in the programmer’s viewport.
4. Understandable. Many existing syntax highlighting methods use regular expression automata, forcing programmers to remember complex state transitions. In our system, people specify coloring rules via productions without considering states.

However, syntax highlighting using our system has a shortcoming: whether it handles the code located after syntax errors, will depend on whether the backend support error-tolerant parsing.

6 Related Research and Comparisons

We present backend-independent semantic actions in order to support our goal, i.e., type safety (especially in AST construction), portability and AST output. There are also related research sharing similar goals to ours.

BNF Converter (BNFC[10][5]) is a compiler construction tool generating parser code for multiple programming languages. BNFC uses a BNF derivative called Labelled BNF, which generates parsers that directly create typed syntax trees.

However, syntax trees created by such parsers are not abstract, as Labelled BNF fails at desugaring syntax. Regarding Fig. 6.1, which is a piece of Labelled BNF grammar for Java `try-catch` clauses. The nonterminal `Catch` creates an algebraic data type (ADT) named `Catch`, while the “labels” in the productions, such as `Catch1` and `Catch2`, create constructors for `Catch`. However, the rule labelled `Catch2` is a syntax sugar to the rule labelled `Catch1`. Hence, ASTs created by Labelled BNF parsers are not well suited for compiler construction or other program processing. They are more of “typed CSTs”, as an abstract syntax should be stripped of its “syntactic sugar” [13] [1]. Typed BNF gives a better solution (Fig. 6.2), by explicitly specifying the construction and eliminating “syntactic sugars”.

Typed BNF is advantageous over Labelled BNF in reusing AST construction across backends. In addition, vanilla BNFs as readable syntax specifications can be generated from Typed BNF by eliminating semantic actions, which disproves Labelled BNF’s denial of semantic actions [5].

```

Catch → "catch" "(" TypeSpec Ident ")" Body { Catch($3, Some($4), $5) }
Catch → "catch" "(" TypeSpec ")" Body      { Catch($3, None, $4) }

```

Figure 6.2: Typed BNF: a piece of Java grammar

Another Tool for Language Recognition (ANTLR[9]) is yet another research closely related to our goal. ANTLR toolchain supports generating parsers for various programming languages, but not as portable as Typed BNF. To get ASTs from ANTLR’s portable parsers, repeating CST-to-AST conversion is needed per backend.

7 Conclusion

We proposed Typed BNF and created a reference implementation, successfully enabling type safety, portability and AST output by our backend-independent semantic actions. We also proved that our type system is sound with respect to the natural semantics of parsing.

According to the previous sections, we conclude the merits of Typed BNF as follows.

- Typed BNF brings type safety, portability and AST output at the same time.
- Typed BNF understands types, which allows automatic type inference. Unlike SAs in ANTLR4 [9] or YACC [6], type annotations are usually not mandatory. This considerably eases the use of semantic actions.
- Typed BNF allows the generated parsers to output ASTs across backends. This is particularly important to scenarios where a user requires parsers but also wants to avoid concrete syntax and focus on abstract syntax.
- Typed BNF performs static type checking before code generation, and reports compile-time errors with precise positions and extra information such as rule names (Fig. 1.3). Pre-generation type checking is usually not available in the existing systems, which makes Typed BNF appealing even when portability is not needed.
- Typed BNF statically checks the grammar and AST construction, even if the backend language is dynamic.

As a bonus, we showed the effectiveness of using Typed BNF for cross-editor syntax highlighting. Such fact suggests that Typed BNF is particularly useful when we do not want to restrict our parser implementation to a specific programming environment.

Yet, there are still some theoretical issues we haven’t addressed. For instance, the proof of our system’s properties does not hold when ϵ rules are allowed in the grammar. However, we believe it is do-able, and we add it to our future plans.

Besides, our system currently does not tell whether a grammar is valid for a backend. For instance, ANTLR4 backends do not support indirect left recursions, and LR parsers do not support ambiguous grammars. This prevents the generated code from working in certain backends due to the limitations of the parser algorithm. In terms of this issue, we think it is feasible to perform grammar transformations in Typed BNF to release restrictions. This is also one of our future plans.

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